

Power Quality improvement using PI and Fuzzy logic controllers based Shunt Active Filters

Authors : Dipen Mistry, Bhupelly Dheeraj, Ravit Gautam, Manmohan singh Meena, Suresh Mikkili

Abstract : In recent years the large scale use of the power electronic equipment has led to an increase of harmonics in the power system. The harmonics results into a poor power quality and have great adverse economical impact on the utilities and customers. Current harmonics are one of the most common power quality problems and are usually resolved by using shunt active filter (SHAF). The main objective of this work is to develop PI and Fuzzy logic controllers (FLC) to analyze the performance of Shunt Active Filter for mitigating current harmonics under balanced and unbalanced source voltage condition for normal load and increased load. FLC offers an outstanding results when source voltages are not ideal. Extensive simulation were carried out with balanced and unbalanced condition. Simulation results validate the superiority of fuzzy logic controller with triangular membership function over the PI controller

Keywords : Power Quality, Harmonics; Active power filter; Shunt active filter; DC link voltage; Total Harmonic Distortion; PI controller; Fuzzy logic controller.

Conference Title : ICEP 2014 : International Conference on Electronic Publications

Conference Location : journal city, WASET

Conference Dates : November 23-23, 2014